

Ways to Develop the Communicative Competence through the Library of Primary Class Students

Jurayeva Turgunoy Umarjonovna¹

¹ Namangan State University, teacher of the Department of Teaching Methodology of Social and Humanities in Primary Education

Abstract:

This article describes ways to develop the communicative competence of elementary school students through reading.

Keywords: competence, communicative, reading, book reading, reading, well-rounded person, library, primary class, students.

Introduction. We can say that one of the most important tasks facing us today is to raise the spiritual and moral environment in our society, to raise our own national values and traditions, human rights and will, to make young people wise and strong. Because the main goal of education and training is to bring up a well-rounded person. The most important tool for us to achieve perfection is definitely the book. The head of our country also took this into account. And reading a book is of inestimable importance in forming such truly human qualities in a person, helping him find his place in life, becoming a real member of society, and broadening his worldview. That is why the head of our state Sh. Mirziyoyev decided to promote reading and publishing. The decision of the President of September 13, 2017 "On the program of comprehensive measures to develop the system of publication and distribution of book products, increase and promote the culture of book reading and reading" and the Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan We can say that the Decisions of the Court of December 14, 2020 "On the program for the development and support of reading culture in 2020-2025" are a clear proof of this . These decisions are explained by the fact that the place and role of the book and reading culture in the spiritual life of the society has been raised to a new level.

Literature analysis. Books help a person to develop in every way. We can say that the role of communicative competence in human development is huge. First, let's talk about the word competence. If we pay attention to the essence of the word competence, this word comes from the English word "competence" which means "to compete", "to compete", "to compete". means Literally translated, it means "ability to compete".

The scientific pedagogical and psychological sources, competence, competence are very complex, multi-part concepts common to many disciplines. Therefore, its interpretations are different both in size and content, and in terms of meaning and logical content.

The essence of the term is also based on concepts such as "efficiency ", "adaptability", "achievement", "success", "comprehensibility", "effectiveness", "readability", "property", "property", "quality", "quantity". is also described.

In the descriptions of the concepts of "competence", "competence", special attention is paid to the following cases:

- ✓ application of knowledge ;
- ✓ personality, characteristics, qualities;
- ✓ of preparation for practical activity;
- ✓ to solve problems, to achieve the necessary results in practice;
- ✓ knowledge, skills, qualifications that ensure the professional activity of a person;
- ✓ of activated (applied) training , knowledge, experiences;
- ✓ directed emotional willpower of a person.

Above, in the process of describing the word competence, each description is inextricably linked with reading. The word "communicative" is actually a Latin word and is a term related to techniques and technologies. If we approach it from a social point of view, it includes the process of information exchange between individuals within a group or organization, within the entire community.

In psychological books, **communicative ability is an ability that improves** communication with other people and provides psychological cohesion in joint activities.[1]

That is why in our motherland, acquiring knowledge, writing books, reading books, creativity are always sacred concepts that show the existence of the nation and what it is capable of. From the Greek philosophers to the scientists of the East and the West, all of them lived forever for thousands of years, became known to the world, and made research and discoveries that will not lose their importance over time, only and only through books. The reason why they are deeply studied by today's generations, and why they often refer to their scientific and educational works is due to the books created by our thinkers.

Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi

Educational views and ideas

- ✓ Coherent and logical presentation of knowledge;
- ✓ demonstration and question-and-answer;
- ✓ of qualifications and skills ;
- ✓ He advised to use knowledge testing methods.

According to him, knowing by "intuition" is partial knowing, while knowing by logical statement shows the important side of true knowing.

The book is an unquenchable light that illuminates the paths of life [2]

As the great poet and thinker Alisher Navoi wrote, "The book is a grateful teacher, the most important source of knowledge and spiritual growth." **A book** is a light that illuminates the paths of life, a source of happiness that gives meaning to a person's life, and we can say that it is a faithful friend who accompanies in any situation. I think that there is no tool as powerful as a book to ensure the spiritual maturity of a person. Therefore, it is known from history that from time immemorial leaders of enlightenment and wise people have invited all mankind to read books and learn from them the secrets of science and manners.

Research methodology. Today, the relevant legal framework has been created in the field of press, publishing and information, and more than 10 laws and more than 30 by-laws have been adopted. 1677 printing enterprises, 118 publishing houses are registered with the state. The National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, equipped with modern technologies, 14 territorial unit information-library centers, about 200 information-resource centers in educational institutions in district and city centers provide information-library services to the population and "World of Books", "Sharq ziyokori" and "Uzdavkitsavdotaminot" complexes have launched book sales services. At the same time, in order to ensure the implementation of the decisions, activities aimed at promoting the culture of reading and reading are ongoing.

Analysis and results. The root of the words "book", "reading", "library" is actually derived from Arabic and serves one purpose, that is, to enrich human spirituality. The reforms implemented in our country to increase the reading culture of young people are not in vain, therefore, the maturity of the future generation is determined by acquiring knowledge and being educated.

The word "*mutolaa*" means reading in Arabic, and today it means a broader concept than reading a book. Books collect the masterpieces of human thought and pass them down from generation to generation. Indeed, no other source can enhance human maturity like books. We can say that every reader will be able to read artistic works or scientific works based on his age group, and to understand the ideas covered more deeply. For this, the child's interests should be thoroughly studied in cooperation with parents, kindergarten, and school, and of course recommendations should be made. As they say, seven neighborhoods to one child, parents are equally responsible for their children's upbringing and their spiritual and cultural development. It is not for nothing that they say that a family that does not read books is a spiritually poor family. Therefore, not only the parents, but also the people around the child, and of course the library staff, should be experts in their profession and choose the right books for the readers, taking into account their interests. In addition, the people who initiate the process of guiding students to read books are their teachers. In the pedagogy of children's reading, the growth of reading according to age is divided into the following stages:

childhood 6-9 years;

transition from childhood to adolescence 10-11 years;

adolescence 12-13 years old;

The transition from adolescence to adolescence is considered to be 14 years.

The age limit of people in this category is flexible, that is, according to the formation of the socio-psychological conditions of the reader, a 10-year-old child can be added to the category of adolescent readers depending on the unique typological characteristics, and 14-year-olds are considered to be adolescents. It will be possible to add to the list of the nature of the category. In order for reading to enter the spiritual life of a child, it is necessary to have an effective and aesthetic preparation in advance.[3]

We aim to teach primary school students to read, we have the opportunity to cover children from the above periods of 6-9 years old and 10-11 years old transitioning from childhood to adolescence. During this period, the students were very curious and active, and if the teacher could give the right direction, there was an opportunity to achieve great goals. At the same time, we can say that 6-11-

year-old students have higher retention processes than others. Communicative competence is well developed in the reader. The reason is that during reading the book, he will have information about how to act and speak in different situations. If we consider the formation of students' communicative competence through "Reading literacy" and "Mother language" lessons in primary grades, we can say that teaching reading is the most effective way.

Conclusions. In conclusion, we can show that teaching students to read is an effective way to develop the communicative competence of elementary school students. Reading has a positive effect on everyone. It is important that we pay the greatest attention to books so that we can make our students grow up as well-rounded individuals. Today, we can say that primary school textbooks have been updated and improved in every way. Now the task is assigned to the teachers, who should recommend books taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the students. If we start this process, that is, if we make students interested in reading books, we will have fulfilled a part of the task set before us. If we manage to organize systematic work through this, we will make our contribution to the realization of the expected "Renaissance" in our country in the future.

References:

1. <https://nrm.uz> page 1-2.
2. <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/kitobkhonlik--buyuk-kelajak-kafolati>
3. <https://tiame.uz/oz/content/kitobkhonlik-kelajak-kafolati>
4. Shavkat Mirziyoyev "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people" Tashkent: Uzbekistan , 2017
5. Uzbek language" Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" state scientific publishing house.
6. Abdulla Kadiri's novel "Bygone Days" Tashkent: "Sharq" publishing house, 2013.
7. "Uzbek folk tales" Tashkent: "Kaldirgoch" publishing house, 2012.
8. Alisher Navoi "Khamsa" Tashkent: "Generation of the New Century", 2015.
9. Mahmudhoja Behbudi "Selected Works" Tashkent: "Spirituality", 1999.
10. Yusuf Khos Hajib " Kutadgu bilig" Tashkent: "Yangi asr avlod", 2019.
11. It is the highest happiness to serve our motherland in the way of its happiness, fortune and great future " Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 2015.
12. Turg'unoy Jo'rayeva " DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS . " EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH Innovative Academy Research Support Center UIF = 8.1 | SJIF = 5.685 A peer reviewed journal 206-210 www.in-academy.uz . Received: 26th February 2023 Accepted: 06th March 2023 Online: 08th March 2023 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7710412>
13. Turgunoy Jorayeva EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH Innovative Academy Research Support Center UIF = 8.1 | SJIF = 5.685 A peer reviewed journal 67-76 www.in-academy.uz . Received: 02nd March 2023 Accepted: 09th March 2023 Online: 10th March 2023 DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7710412>